

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication activities v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G-IA	5G Infrastructure Association
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
ETNO	European Telecommunications Network Operators
EU	European Union
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GA	Grant Agreement
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Communications,
IBN	Intent-Based interfaces
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MVNO	Mobile Virtual Network Operator
MWC	Mobile World Congress
NetApps	Network Applications
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
OTT	Over-the-top
R&I	Research and Innovation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SB	Steering Board
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
T	Task
TB	Technical Board
T&L	Transport and Logistics

UC	Use Case
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes VITAL-5G's Dissemination and Communication Plans, as defined in Task 6.1 ("Dissemination & communication activities") of the Work Package 6 ("Dissemination, Communication & Standardization"). Task 6.1 will define all dissemination and communication (D&C) activities, as well as the tools that will be used by the project partners to engage with the relevant stakeholders.

The deliverable details VITAL-5G's outreach strategy and framework and outlines the project's envisaged D&C activities, along with their Key performance Indicators (KPIs). It is aimed to be a guiding document for the projects' partners in order to align with the D&C main objectives and planned activities. The Deliverable also provides an overview of the D&C activities for the first five months of the project.

The deliverable reports on the planned activities of VITAL-5G that aim to ensure far-reaching dissemination and communication of the project's results and outcomes. These activities, that are clearly defined in the deliverable, will be carried out throughout the project lifetime and will maximise the impact of the Project. The deliverable also reports on the first round of D&C activities that have been carried out in the first five months of the project. More specifically, the project has been very actively disseminated, having three papers by project partners published in conference proceedings and summits. Furthermore, the project partners have participated in three public events, adding to the exposure of the project as well as assisting in promoting the research that is carried out. Finally, the project has been disseminated in 5G PPP related activities (i.e., 6th issue of the 5G European Annual Journal), while the first project press release has been issued.

1 Introduction

The VITAL-5G project aims to advance offered transport & logistics (T&L) services by engaging significant logistics stakeholders (Sea and River port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators), as well as innovative SMEs and offering them an open and secure virtualized 5G environment to test, validate and verify T&L related cutting-edge Network Applications (NetApps).

Due to the numerous technological novelties and their applications produced by the VITAL-5G project, their dissemination to the maximum number of relevant stakeholders is a key success factor for the project success. The dissemination of the developed ideas and the obtained results to a wide audience, ranging from the research community to non-scientific public, is critical for the overall success and the impact of VITAL-5G on society. Work Package 6 aims at increasing the visibility of VITAL-5G by coordinating the activities related to the dissemination of the results and the communication of the proposed solutions. To that end, a set of tools has been created to promote the VITAL-5G solutions both to expert and non-expert audience. This deliverable of WP6 provides the initial dissemination and communication plan of VITAL-5G.

This deliverable is an outcome of the activities of T6.1 “Dissemination & communication activities”. This task at hand, in addition to task T6.2 “Standardization contributions”, T6.3 “Capacity building programme” and T6.4 “5G PPP collaboration activities” will orchestrate consortium efforts towards maximizing the overall impact of the project, all of which will be held within the framework of Work Package 6 ‘Dissemination, Communication & Standardization.

This report is the first of a series of three consecutive deliverables related to the D&C activities of the project. D6.2 first details the project’s D&C tools and activities, its plan, and the evaluation criteria, while it sets the basis for the upcoming D6.3 and D6.4 (interim and final report, respectively), which will detail the D&C activities until the end of the project. The next deliverables, Namely D6.3 ‘Dissemination and Communication activities v2.0’ at month 18, and finally D6.4 ‘Dissemination and Communication activities - Final’ at month 36, will further detail and provide the updates of the implemented D&C actions throughout the project lifetime.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 6.1 Dissemination & communication activities	This task will define the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) plans and select appropriate tools to be used by the Consortium for internal /external communication.	Chapter 3 Chapter 4 Chapter 5	D&C plans have been identified in Chapters 3, 4 and 5 of the document, along with the tools to be used by the partners for communication.
	The main elements of the D&C plan will be tasks,	Chapter 2	The Tasks and audiences of the D&C activities have been identified in

	responsible partners, materials used, audience addressed and timing.	Chapter 3 Chapter 4 Chapter 5 Chapter 6	Chapters 3 and 4. The D&C plan is presented in Chapter 5, while the material to be used for the D&C activities is presented in Chapter 2. Finally, chapter 6 provides the timing for the Activities along with target values (KPIs).
	In addition, the D&C plan includes: (a) project identity definition; (b) target group definition; (c) issue of dissemination material; (d) selection of the appropriate communication activities; (e) evaluation of the communication activities performed	Chapter 2 Chapter 3 Chapter 4 Chapter 5 Chapter 6	<p>The project identity is presented in Chapter 2, while target groups, along with the selection of the appropriate activities, have been identified in Chapters 3 and 4 for Communication and Dissemination Activities respectively.</p> <p>The phases of the Dissemination and Communication Activities Plan and the link between Phases and Target Audience, Channels and Goals are highlighted in Chapter 5.</p> <p>Finally, the evaluation of communication and dissemination activities performed is presented in Chapter 6.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
D6.2: Dissemination and Communication activities v1.0			
First version of the dissemination and communication plan and report containing the dissemination and communication activities implemented.			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The overall structure of this deliverable can be summarized as follows:

- Chapter 2 introduces the project identity;
- Chapter 3 provides an overview of the communication objectives, strategy, tools, audience and stakeholders, along with some updates on communication activities;
- Chapter 4 provides an overview of the dissemination objectives, strategy, tools, audiences and stakeholders;
- Chapter 5 provides an overview of the plan of D&C activities;
- Chapter 6 defined the measurable indicators and metrics (KPIs) of the D&C activities;
- Chapter 7 concludes the deliverable and sets expectations for next steps.

2 Project Identity

This section describes the dissemination & communication (D&C) channels that have been used in order to establish the VITAL-5G project brand identity and to ensure that all D&C activities of the project, including reports, website, flyers, posters, presentations and banners will have a professional and uniform look. This uniform brand identity greatly facilitates recognition by the different stakeholders that will be engaged with the project activities.

2.1 Project Logo

A project logo, as shown in Figure 1, has been designed to help the external audience easily identify VITAL-5G project and to increase the VITAL-5G project visibility by providing a corporate identity from the very beginning of the project. The logo has been made available to the consortium to use for official communication purposes. It serves as the basis for all further promotional materials, as well as the website, in order to ensure consistent branding across all D&C channels.

Figure 1: VITAL-5G Logo

2.2 Project Presentation

This Section presents VITAL-5G's Power Point Presentation, which aims to establish a strong visual presentation of the project. The VITAL-5G Presentation initially provides general information for the project along with information about the project participants. The VITAL-5G Vision, its Objectives and Concept are then described in a thorough way. Finally, the VITAL-5G Use cases are presented. The VITAL-5G Project Presentation, along with the Project Presentation Template, have been uploaded in the Project Repository and have been shared with all the partners. A snapshot of the Presentation Template is shown in Figure 2, while the full VITAL-5G Project Presentation can be found on the VITAL-5G website at the following link: https://www.vital5g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/VITAL5G_Project-Presentation.pdf.

Figure 2: VITAL-5G Project Presentation Template

2.3 Project Public Summary

This Section presents the VITAL-5G Project’s public summary, which provides information about the project goals, its vision, and describes its use cases. The Project Public Summary is an informative document about the VITAL-5G Project, providing a succinct and accurate description of the Project Concept, its Experimentation Infrastructure and its Targeted Trials. It should be noted that the VITAL-5G Project summary has been also featured in the sixth issue of the European 5G Annual Journal, which was released at the end of May 2021.

The full text of the public summary is provided in the following Subsection. This refined information serves as the project summary to be used by all partners for their relevant D&C activities.

2.3.1 VITAL-5G Project Summary

Project Concept and Goals

The strategic objective of VITAL-5G is to create an open, virtualized and flexible experimentation facility comprised of an intelligent virtual platform, three distributed European 5G-testbeds (Antwerp, Athens and Galati (Danube) and associated vertical infrastructure, to enable the testing and validation of Network Applications (NetApps) for Transport and Logistics (T&L) services in real-life conditions, utilizing 5G connectivity. To that end, VITAL-5G engages significant logistics stakeholders (Sea/River port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators), Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), as well as innovative SME experimenters, thus prioritizing a multi-modal focus and addressing challenges of the entire 5G-enabled T&L ecosystem.

VITAL-5G’s concept of NetApps is defined as *virtual applications that are built and distributed through self-contained packages comprising their virtual images and metadata, descriptors and scripts that simplify their composition in service chains formed by virtualized and physical functions*. Multiple NetApps will be developed, enhanced and validated over the complementary facilities offered by VITAL-5G infrastructure, while the

invitation towards 3rd party experimenters will allow for external SMEs to build and validate their T&L solutions and services utilizing the VITAL-5G NetApps and experimentation facilities.

Figure 3: VITAL-5G System Architecture

The VITAL-5G conceptual architecture, shown in Figure 3 is structured in two layers: i) the VITAL-5G Open Platform implementing all tools and services for design, on-boarding, deployment, orchestration, monitoring, validation and diagnostics applied to T&L vertical services and ii) the three 5G-enabled T&L testbeds.

The VITAL-5G platform will consist of a Service Portal for T&L services lifecycle management and an Open Online Repository to share NetApps from different software developers. The coordinated actions of these two functional blocks will allow VITAL-5G’s vertical stakeholders to design, onboard, instantiate, manage and benchmark their T&L NetApps. The platform will support a multitude of experimentation tools, such as Intent-Based interfaces (IBN), programmatic APIs, Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, analytics dashboards and more, to facilitate and enhance the experimentation experience.

Experimentation Infrastructure and Targeted Trials

Three industry-driven use cases (UCs) have been selected for trials over the VITAL-5G experimentation facilities.

Use Case 1: Automated vessel transport – Antwerp facility

In the Port of Antwerp UC, 5G connectivity and slicing will be used to control semi-autonomous vessels. A real-time digital twin will be built around the vessel to support the remotely controlled vessels. In parallel, real-time route planning will be foreseen to optimize the port operations and to avoid idle times. It will be based on

berthing time slots provided by the port authorities and terminal operators, while the optimization will be performed based on ML/AI methodologies.

The Antwerp 5G-testbed is based on i) infrastructure of Telenet's (MNO) Innovation Centre, ii) connectivity, infrastructure and system built for the 5G-Blueprint project¹ and iii) connectivity and supporting infrastructure built for Telenet's 5G commercial launch in Flanders. The complete system will provide a fully standalone (SA) 5G network supporting 3GPP Rel.16 and will further comprise a virtualized 5G Core, MEC nodes and multiple end devices, supporting end-to-end slicing.

Use Case 2: Warehouse/freight logistics - Athens facility

The Athens based UC targets the automation and remote operation of freight logistics, effectively instantiating the concept of a Smart Warehouse. The target is to facilitate and optimize day-to-day warehousing operations, through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and the easy deployment and control/operation of such services via NetApps. To that end, the UC will investigate concepts such as lean warehousing (elimination of time waste), in-warehouse route optimization with obstacle avoidance, remote surveillance and control, human-AGV collaboration, intelligent product inspection and more.

The Athens experimentation facility is comprised of the 5G-testbed owned by OTE (MNO), created in the context of the 5G-EVE project², and the state-of-the-art logistic-hub of DIAKINISIS, the largest 3rd Party Logistics Greek operator. The 5G-testbed will be upgraded from its current Non-Stand Alone (NSA) version to 3GPP Rel.16 compliant SA and will provide indoor and outdoor connectivity over fiber backbone.

Use Case 3: Data-enabled assisted navigation – Galati (Danube) facility

This UC is focused on the implementation of a data-enabled assisted navigation application using IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati river port on a ship and barges. The UC will leverage on IoT, data fusion, ingestion, post-processing, fraud detection and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship insurance purposes based on AI/ML mechanisms over 5G connectivity. The UC application will allow a safer port operation and more secure navigation, even in severe weather and water conditions.

The Romanian 5G-testbed is based on the Orange Romania (MNO) testbed platform, using parts of the commercial 5G network and experimental opensource components, created by the 5G-EVE project². The testbed, which is currently a Rel.15 compatible NSA network, will be progressively upgraded to a Rel.16 SA network and supports various orchestrators (ONAP/OSM), VNF onboarding and network slicing.

Targeted Innovations

VITAL-5G aims to minimize the knowledge/expertise gap between telecom providers, vertical industries and application developers through the promotion and validation of NetApps. To that end specific innovative results, stemming from three innovation areas, will be delivered by the project, as depicted in Figure 4.

¹ <https://www.5gblueprint.eu/>

² <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>

Figure 4: VITAL-5G’s innovation map

3 Communication Activities

Communication activities about the project and results, involve the use of available channels and tools by the project's partners to reach multiple audiences that include both the media and the public. VITAL-5G's communication activities mainly aim to inform and reach out to society and show the benefits of the research work performed under the Horizon 2020 framework and specifically within the VITAL-5G project.

This Chapter presents the target audiences of VITAL-5G's communication activities and highlights the communication channels that have been collectively and strategically chosen by the consortium in order to be effective and proportionate in scale to the actions and goal of the project.

3.1 Target Audiences

The main objectives of VITAL'5G communication strategy are: i) to create an active community of interested stakeholders and potential users and collect knowledge and requirements considered by the project; ii) to create awareness of the project among the full range of stakeholders impacted by the results activities and iii) to formulate adapted key messages and prepare adapted communication material. Table 2 provides an outline of the target audiences of the project and their potential interest in VITAL-5G activities.

Table 2: VITAL-5G Communication Target Audience groups

Target Group	Description	Interest in the project
SMEs and industry	Stakeholders from industry, network operators, SMEs and entrepreneurs, operating in the 5G and T&L domains (e.g., OTT providers, application and NetApps developers, T&L service providers)	Use of VITAL-5G Experimentation Platform for accelerating their service deployment; Promoting VITAL-5G in operations and in their Research & Innovation (R&I) activities for new service development; Amplify innovation in 5G-enabled T&L services by blending VITAL-5G outcomes with in-house technology components and developed technologies
Mass media channels	Traditional media channels (i.e., newspapers, magazines, radio) Social media channels (i.e., LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)	Inform about the project through flyers, banners, videos, press releases related to the added value of the project and the benefits offered to the society
Clusters	European initiatives and clusters, research communities, associations, (e.g., ETNO, NetWorld2020, Digital Business Innovation, Digital Agenda, Innovation Union, etc.)	Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (i.e., white papers); Communicate project's results to their members; Participation in project's events for knowledge exchange
General Public	General public, end-users and anyone interested in the project	Non-technical articles based on project's results;

		Stimulate innovation in unexpected groups of society
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3.2 Project Website

The VITAL-5G project website was launched on January 1st, 2021. The main objectives of the website are i) to promote the project's public image and serve as a main online access point for the different target groups; ii) to serve as an information source, highlighting project objectives, activities, outcomes and relevant updates; and iii) to serve as a repository of information. The website (see Figure 5) is publicly accessible and also features a restricted area that is only accessible to project partners, the EC project scientific officer and the project review panel team. It is a fully functional and responsive web portal that contains comprehensive information on the VITAL-5G aims and objectives with easy access and a friendly interface to retrieve information and any public material generated within the project, as well as materials gathered via the various work packages activities and 5G PPP-related activities. Its design methodology and associated technologies are fully detailed in the Deliverable D6.1 "Project website and social media presence".

Figure 5: VITAL-5G Website Responsive Views

The VITAL-5G Website is undoubtedly the most important component of VITAL-5G's communication toolset, as it inclusively contains all information about the project, its progress and its findings. It is also the tool that can easily reach all the target audience tiers of the project.

3.3 Social Media

VITAL-5G project social media accounts, namely Twitter, LinkedIn page, and YouTube Channel, were launched on January 1st, 2021, as part of the communication tools that will be utilised within the project. These three VITAL-5G social media channels are also fully detailed in the Deliverable D6.1 "Project website and social media presence".

The social media channels are specifically used to communicate and disseminate project progress and results in a way that is not overly technical and can be easily understood by non-specialists and the public audience.

3.3.1 Twitter

VITAL-5G'S Twitter channel (<https://twitter.com/5gVital>) was the first communication channel of the project. A screenshot of the Twitter account can be seen in Figure 6. At the time of writing (24/05/2021), VITAL-5G Twitter account has 104 followers and follows 94 accounts.

Figure 6: VITAL-5G Twitter Page

Regarding the performance of our Twitter account, numbers seem overall very promising. The account has gained a wide audience in a short time, with some very influential followers (e.g., several followers of VITAL-5G have a very wide network of thousands of followers), which means that when these accounts interact with VITAL-5G (i.e. like or retweet a post) their network of followers can also see this post, thus increasing vastly the reach of VITAL-5G project.

It should be noted that the Twitter account displays a constant upward trend, with the number of tweet impressions, profile visits, mentions, and followers increasing every month.

3.3.2 LinkedIn

VITAL-5G's LinkedIn account, as shown in Figure 7 is a LinkedIn Page numbering 60 followers at the time of writing (24/05/2021). The LinkedIn account displays an upward trend as well, having earned more than 2350 impressions for its first five months of operation.

Figure 7: VITAL-5G LinkedIn Page

3.4 Promotional material

The promotional material that will be prepared in the scope of VITAL-5G aims at properly presenting the project, the motivation behind carrying out its work, its technological framework and context of the field, as well as the objectives it intends to accomplish. Over the course of the project 3 technical brochures will be issued, providing information about the technical and scientific achievements of the project, while 3 non-technical brochures/factsheets will be issued describing the potential project applications and services in a more accessible manner. A number of project flyers, posters and roll-up banners will also be created for display in conferences and in exhibition booths. The brochures will be also distributed to local universities, schools, city councils and other relevant organizations. The Project Factsheet has already been produced and is presented in the following subsection.

3.4.1 Project Factsheet

The current Subsection presents the VITAL-5G Project Factsheet. The factsheet has been created as a one-page presentation of the project's major data, where project's key points are emphasised concisely.

A brief summary of the project is given, as well as some basic information about the project, such as the topic of the project, the start date and duration, the budget, the consortium composition and the name of the coordinating organisation.

Furthermore, the strategic objectives of the project are presented, while an overview of the Project’s Use Cases is provided. Moreover, the logos of all Partners participating in the project are presented (in the form of clickable images that redirect to each specific partner’s website address), along with acknowledgement of the EU Funding. Finally, on the upper right corner of the project, there are three clickable images that respectively redirect to the project website, the VITAL-5G Twitter profile and the project’s LinkedIn profile. The project Factsheet is uploaded on the Project’s Repository and shared with all project Partners and is presented in Figure 8.

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

www.vital5g.eu
 [5gVital](#)
 [vital-5g-project](#)

About VITAL-5G Project

The VITAL-5G project has the vision to advance the offered transport & logistics (T&L) services by engaging significant logistics stakeholders (Sea and River port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators, etc.) as well as innovative SMEs and offering them an open and secure virtualized 5G environment to test, validate and verify their T&L related cutting-edge Network Applications (NetApps).

Objectives

- 01** Foster the development and sharing of novel vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic NetApps for the T&L sector
- 02** Deliver a testing and validation experimentation facility that will allow T&L stakeholders to deploy and benchmark the performance of their NetApps
- 03** Showcase the added value of 5G connectivity for multi-modal logistics services across European roads, seas and rivers
- 04** Provide customized and virtualized access to network and T&L infrastructure resources, enabling service provisioning to 3rd parties
- 05** Enable novel business models development for open, integrated and cooperative services across multiple domains
- 06** Foster the development and advancement of a T&L centred ecosystem by bringing together key vertical stakeholders with SMEs

Project Start: 01/01/2021
EU Budget: € 4,777,525
Instrument: ICT-41-2020 - 5G PPP – 5G innovations for verticals with third party services
Duration: 36 Months
Coordinator: WINGS ICT Solutions
Consortium: 16 partners from 6 countries

Use Cases

- Use Case 1**
Automated vessel transport (Antwerp Port)
- Use Case 2**
Data enabled assisted navigation & customs operations for ships (Galati Danube river port)
- Use Case 3**
Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics)

Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No101016567

Figure 8: VITAL-5G Project Factsheet

3.5 Project Poster

The VITAL-5G Project Poster has been produced, with an eye-catching design, illustrating the aim of the project along with its objectives. The poster represents the main VITAL-5G design idea, with the goal of making the project easily clearly identifiable and consistent in its branding. This poster, shown in Figure 9, will be used to showcase the project at conferences, meetings, workshops and events and will effectively communicate the project vision and objectives in a brief and concise way. The poster is uploaded on the Project’s Repository and has been shared with all project Partners.

VITAL 5G

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Vertical Innovations in Transport and Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

5G PPP

About

The VITAL-5G Project has the vision to enable the creation of 5G-enhanced services for the Transport & Logistics (T&L) industry by bridging the knowledge/expertise gap between the T&L sector, telecommunication experts and application developers. VITAL-5G will engage key logistics stakeholders (sea and river port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators, etc.) and innovative SMEs, offering them an open and secure virtualised 5G environment to test and validate their T&L-related, cutting-edge Network Applications (NetApps).

Project Start: 01/01/2021
EU Budget: € 4,777,525
Instrument: ICT-41-2020
Duration: 36 Months
Consortium: 16 partners from 6 countries

USE CASES

Use Case 1	Use Case 2	Use Case 3
Port Digital Twin – Automated Vessel Transport (Antwerp Port)	Data enabled assisted navigation & customs operations for ships (Galati Danube river port)	Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics)

Consortium

Project Coordinator: **WINGS** (ICT solutions)

Partners: **Beia** (smart systems), **DHL** (EXEL SUPPLY CHAIN), **DIAKINISIS** (Logistics Services), **DIGITTRANS**, **eBOS**, **TEHNOPOL GALATI**, **mec**, **Incelligent** (Next generation - smart logistics), **inlecom**, **NAVROM** (CENTRALA DE NAVIGARE FLUVIALA ROMANIA), **NEXTWORKS** (Networks for Logistics), **orange**, **OTE**, **SEAFAR**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016567

Figure 9: VITAL-5G Project Poster

3.6 Press Releases and TV/Radio Interviews

VITAL-5G will publish at least 6 press releases in order to show major achievements and the potential of 5G as a future-proof technology for T&L services. The content of the first press release is already being prepared and is expected to be issued by M6 (June 2021). Furthermore, VITAL-5G will attempt to reach the general audience via TV/radio interviews conducted by the partners in the course of the project.

3.6.1 Project Kick-off Releases

Following the kick-off meeting of the project, an article introducing the project, its goals and its consortium composition has been published on the VITAL-5G website “News and Events” section (<https://www.vital5g.eu/category/news-events/>), along with other project-related news. The Project-kick off Release can be seen in Figure 10. Moreover, several of the project partners have sought to endorse the project by promoting their engagement in the VITAL-5G project through their own channels, as part of the collaborative D&C efforts. The first of these articles are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12, published by eBOS Technologies and WINGS ICT Solutions respectively on their own website’s blogs (<http://www.ebos.com.cy/new-h2020-ict-41-5g-project-vital-5g-kicks-off> and <https://www.wings-ict-solutions.eu/news/project-managers-on-the-vital-5g-project>). Further project-related press releases, to be published by partners, will be included in the future iterations of this D&C report.

New H2020 ICT-41 5G Project VITAL-5G kicks off!

News & Events

On the 26th and 27th of January 2021, the new 5G Research and Innovation project VITAL-5G Project “Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities” held a successful online kick-off meeting with the participation of partners and the coordination of WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS

VITAL-5G is part of 5G PPP Phase 3 and will last for 3 years. The project will showcase the added-value of 5G connectivity for the European transport & logistics (T&L) sector by adopting a multi-modal approach containing major logistics hubs for freight and passengers (sea ports, river ports, warehouse/logistics hubs, highways, etc.) as well as the respective stakeholders (road operators, port authorities, 3rd party logistics operators), thus creating an end-to-end chain of connected T&L services accommodating the entire continent.

During the meeting, all 16 partners of the consortium introduced their organisations and the discussion was mainly focused on the role of each partner in the project and the work that needs to be performed under each Work Package. Moreover, the main goal was to establish a common vision for the project and lay out the project management framework.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016567.

Figure 10: VITAL-5G Project Kick-off Release

eBOS Technologies About WiseBOS ERP Research & Development Blog Support Contact Us

New H2020 ICT-41 5G Project VITAL-5G kicks off!

On the 26 and 27 of January 2021, a new 5G Research and Innovation project VITAL-5G: Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities held a successful online kick-off meeting with the participation of 16 partners and the coordination of WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE (WINGS ICT Solutions) by Konstantinos Trichias.

VITAL-5G is part of 5G PPP Phase 3b ICT-41 projects and will last for 3 years. The pan-European Transport & Logistics (T&L) eco-system is considered one of the main adopters of 5G, and as such, the successful transfer of 5G-empowered services from trials/pilot stages to production depends highly on the availability of flexible and intuitive tools and APIs for design, management and orchestration of their services. VITAL-5G prioritises this ambition and plans to overcome, through its intuitive and production-ready NetApps orchestration platform with open repository, various limitations that exist today for industry verticals keen to design and deploy T&L virtualised services in a 5G network.

Mr. Christos Skoufis, Dr. George Guirgis, and Vasilis Machamint R&D Project Managers, represented eBOS Technologies at the online kick-off-meeting. During the meeting all the partners introduced their organisations and the discussion was mainly focused on the role of each partner in the project and the work that needs to be performed under each Work Package, especially during the first 6 months of the project. Moreover, the main goal was to establish a common vision for the project.

EBOS will lead the Quality assurance of the project and will have the responsibility of organizing and supervising quality review/peer reviews for all deliverables including the implementation of the quality management plan. EBOS will be also in charge of performing project quality evaluation criteria, risk assessment, continuous monitoring, triggering quality assurance project reviews, risk assessment procedures, evaluation measurements and producing risk and quality review reports.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016567.

Figure 11: VITAL-5G Project Kick-off Article on eBOS Website

Project managers on the VITAL-5G Project.

JANUARY 25, 2021, NEWS

5G AI MEC

Figure 12: VITAL-5G Project Kick-off Article on WINGS Website

3.6.2 First Press Release

The content of the First Press Release has been prepared in May 2021 by EBOS, in English language, and is presented in Annex II. This first press release mainly aims to announce important steps and results of the project, while the next press releases will be issued over the course of the project to announce project developments and important milestones reached. The press release will be translated by the consortium partners in their native language and they will be channeled to appear in a number of local electronic and printed media. (i.e., newspapers, online newspapers, magazines etc.)

3.7 Video Clips

Prior experience by the project partners has revealed that short video clips are an extremely powerful tool to communicate projects. They serve to create awareness across the general public on the results of the project and illustrate concepts and the impact of the project in an efficient way, increasing the visibility and public acknowledgement of the project. VITAL-5G aims to produce at least 3 video clips, which will cover the VITAL-5G general ideas, demonstrations and presentations and will include non-technical information about the project, targeting specifically the non-expert general audience and end-users. The videos will be available at the project's website and its YouTube channel during the entire project's lifetime, while a dedicated link will be used in order to request feedback from the audience.

3.8 Newsletters

Periodic Newsletters will be produced by VITAL-5G with input and support from the project partners. The Newsletters will provide information on project progress and results as well as links to public deliverables,

articles, news, events and support to the communication campaigns of the project partners. Newsletters will be made available on the project website, in order to improve visibility of the project via electronic means, while subscription to the newsletter will be possible from the website. Also, the newsletters will be distributed to different mailing lists, to foster inter-communication with other relevant research actions, projects and technical communities at European, national and regional level. The first newsletter issue will be released in month M6 (June 2021), while the next newsletters will be issued every 6 months.

3.9 Public Engagement

VITAL-5G consortium members will follow a set of strategies to interact with the general public (e.g., non-scientists, secondary schools) and inform them about the effect of the VITAL-5G results in their everyday life. Public engagement activities will aim to create awareness regarding the societal benefits of 5G technologies on Transport & Logistics (T&L) services. This set of activities will include the use of social media, online video-clips, the participation of VITAL-5G partners at public talks at schools and at university open days, as well as their participation at T&L-related events that are organised by local or national authorities.

3.10 European Disclaimer

All published communication material will include a link to the VITAL-5G website where further information can be obtained. In addition, for all material and publications, the EU emblem will be displayed as funding organ together with the following text “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016567”.

4 Dissemination Activities

The overall aim of the VITAL-5G dissemination strategy is to disclose project results that can be used by specific target audiences to progress their own work, i.e., to build upon the knowledge generated by VITAL-5G, utilising the advancement of technology, science, industry and policy. Target audiences of the project have been identified, as well as specific dissemination objectives, which will be tailored to the needs and profile of the target audience. A major element for the dissemination of the project will also relate to the joint and coordinated participation in relevant activities of the 5G PPP and the 5G Infrastructure Association (5G-IA). VITAL-5G will contribute throughout the course of the project to the various brochures and other material coordinated at 5G PPP level, as requested by the 5G-IA and the Full5G 5G PPP Project. VITAL-5G has already contributed to the “European 5G Annual Journal” for 2021, as already mentioned in Section 2.3.

The dissemination activities can be broadly summed up into three categories:

1. Publications
 - a. Peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals
 - b. Conference papers
 - c. White papers
2. Events
 - a. Conferences
 - b. Exhibitions
 - c. Workshops, demonstrations and seminars
3. Networking
 - a. Relevant H2020 Projects
 - b. Pan-European Stakeholders
 - c. Standardization bodies
 - d. European Technology Platform ALICE – (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe)
 - e. 5G PPP and its Working Groups

4.1 Target Audience

The Target Audiences of the VITAL-5G Project, along with the specific dissemination objectives of each target audience group are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: VITAL-5G Dissemination Target Audience groups

Target Audience	Description	Dissemination objectives
Academia & Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)	Institutions primarily for education and early research for expanding their academic skills	To consider the results in updated curricula, advanced courses and new R&I initiatives
Public R&I	Institutions with innovation-oriented R&D and technology transfer (e.g., EU Investment Bank, Start-Up Europe, EC Digital Innovation Hubs)	To adopt the results in technology transfer and new R&I initiatives with industry
MNOs and Mobile Virtual Network Operators (MVNOs);	As key players in 5G technology market, they will be informed about the project’s	To adopt the results for enhancing their infrastructure and network functions for supporting new T&L

Telecom Infrastructure providers	outcomes and the possibility of adopting the results in their networks and services.	services with guaranteed SLAs supporting OPEX reductions
Industrial equipment vendors	Private companies that maintain R&I groups for new product and services, e.g., telecom vendors, tier-1/tier-2 suppliers	To adopt the results in product and service roadmaps related to network monitoring, management and security
Authorities	Governmental agencies and authorities mainly concerned with policy setting (e.g., road traffic, railway traffic, port traffic authorities)	To consider the results in policy and new regulatory developments for T&L services
Developers from Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)	Technology providers, application service providers and developers of new applications creating strong links with academia, RTOs and leading industrial entities, creating a strong value chain	To adopt the results for developing new innovative T&L applications, new NetApps and to create strong links with industry and academia
Public/Private T&L associations	Initiatives that leverage public and private resources and funds for joint undertakings (e.g., 5G PPP, EIT Digital, European Private Equity, AET, ISF, CLELAT, ELS, ESCF, etc.)	To consider the results in the planning of joint public and private undertakings
5G related organisations	<u>Telecom:</u> ETNO, GSMA, NGMN; <u>International:</u> 5GForum, 5GMF, IMT-2020; <u>Complementary domains:</u> BDVA, NESSI	To consider the results in new 5G releases specifications, establish new strategic goals and strengthen networking activities

4.2 Publications

The research outcomes of the VITAL-5G project will be published in high-impact, scientific (peer reviewed) journals, magazines and conference papers. An indicative shortlist of high impact factor journals and magazines in which the VITAL-5G partners will seek to publish articles are presented in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively, without however excluding the possibility to pursue other publications as well. The project partners can also publish to other scientific journals and magazines which focus on topics that are relevant to the activities of VITAL-5G. The research outcomes of the project are also going to be presented in Scientific (peer-reviewed) Conferences, while an indicative list of the Conferences in which the VITAL-5G partners intend to present the project results can be found in Table 6.

It should be noted that all VITAL-5G publications will be deposited in repositories enlisted in Open AIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), such as ZENODO, in a machine-readable electronic copy. To ensure the open access to the deposited publications, VITAL-5G consortium partners will be free to choose between self-archiving (“green” Open Access) and open access publishing (“gold” Open access). A live repository for registering and monitoring the publications of all VITAL-5G partners is maintained throughout the project.

Table 4: Indicative list of Journals

Journal	Impact Factor	URL
IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications	11.42	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=49
IEEE Access	3.745	https://ieeaccess.ieee.org/
IEEE Pervasive Computing	4.418	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7756
IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking,	3.315	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=90
IEEE Internet Computing	4.231	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=4236
Journal of Network and Computer Applications	5.570	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-network-and-computer-applications
Ad Hoc Networks	3.643	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/ad-hoc-networks
Computer Networks	3.111	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/computer-networks
Computer Communications	2.816	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/computer-communications
MDPI Sensors	3.275	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors
MDPI Electronics	2.412	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/electronics

Table 5: Indicative list of Magazines

Magazine	Impact Factor	URL
IEEE Communications Magazine	11.052	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=35
IEEE Network Magazine	8.808	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=65

4.3 Events

VITAL-5G consortium members will contribute to relevant international and national events by participating in exhibitions through booths, posters, flyers and presentations in order to raise the stakeholders' awareness and facilitate knowledge sharing, thus increasing the project impact. Furthermore, the VITAL-5G partners will participate in conferences and other events that will allow to present thoroughly the project results and will be involved in workshops participation and organization. Participations in such events will leverage the engagement of VITAL-5G with industrial actors as a vehicle to inform relevant stakeholders and incentivise the project's business plan and targeted outputs. An indicative list of targeted events, including conferences and exhibitions by VITAL-5G is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Indicative list of Events

Event Name	Type of Event	URL
Mobile World Congress (MWC)	Exhibition	https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/
European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)	Conference and Exhibition	https://eucnc.eu/
ITS World Congress	Exhibition	https://itsworldcongress.com/
IPIC 2021	Conference	https://www.pi.events/
Intermodal Europe	Exhibition	https://www.intermodal-events.com/en/home.html
IEEE GLOBECOM	Conference	https://globecom2021.ieee-globecom.org/
IEEE ICC	Conference	https://icc2021.ieee-icc.org/
IEEE 5G Summit	Summit	http://www.5gsummit.org/
IEEE INFOCOM	Conference	https://infocom2021.ieee-infocom.org/
ACM MobiCom	Conference	https://www.sigmobile.org/mobicom/2021/
IEEE VTC	Conference	https://events.vtsociety.org/vtc2021-spring/
IEEE ICME	Conference	https://2021.ieeeicme.org/
IEEE BlackSeaCom	Conference	https://blackseacom2021.ieee-blackseacom.org/

4.4 Interaction with 5G PPP Working Groups

The Work Package activities, and more specifically the Task 6.4 (“5G PPP collaboration activities”) activities, will include participation by the members of the consortium: in the Steering Board (SB) (mainly by the Project Coordinator), in the Technical Board (5G-TB) (mainly by the Technical Manager), as well as in various Working Groups (WGs) already set up for the previous 5G-PPP Phases and in 5G PPP fora.

VITAL-5G has declared from the first months of the project its involvement in most of the Working Groups (WGs) related to 5G PPP. The contribution of the VITAL-5G per WG are summarized in Table 7, where the main contributors of VITAL-5G in each WG are listed. The criteria of selecting the responsible people on behalf of VITAL-5G stem mainly from their general expertise and the expertise of their organisations, combined with previous expertise in participation to 5G PPP activities and its WGs.

Table 7: VITAL-5G Contributors to the different WGs established by the 5G-IA and the 5G-PPP

5G PPP Working Group	VITAL-5G Contributing Partners
Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation (TMV) WG	WINGS
Vision and Societal Challenges WG	INLECOM BEIA Orange Romania
Software Network WG	Orange Romania IMEC
5G Architecture WG	Orange Romania OTE
5G Security WG	Orange Romania BEIA
Trials WG	BEIA EBOS
Automotive WG	IMEC BEIA
SME WG	EBOS INLECOM BEIA

4.5 Initial Dissemination Activities

Given the experience and high interest of the partners of the consortium, dissemination activities worth mentioning have been initiated since the very early stages of the project. The following subsections summarize the dissemination activities (publications and participation in events) for the first five months of the project.

4.5.1 Scientific Paper Publications

Even from the early stages of the project, VITAL-5G partners have seized opportunities to reach out to the research community with early results of their work performed in the context of VITAL 5G. The first publications of the project are summarized in Table 8.

4.5.2 Participation in Events

Table 9 lists all the events that VITAL-5G partners attended during the first five months of the project. The events consist of presentations in webinars, Summits and online industrial events.

Table 8: VITAL-5G Scientific Paper Publications

Partner(s)	Type of publication	Title	Author(s)	Title of the Periodical or the series	Year of Publication
BEIA, ORO	Publication in Conference proceedings	Advanced 5G Architectures for Future NetApps and Verticals	Cristian Patachia-Sultanoiu, Alexandru Vulpe, Ion Bogdan, Oana Badita, George Suciu, Bogdan Rusti	IEEE International Black Sea Conference on Communications and Networking (BlackSeaCom 2021)	2021
WINGS, NXW, IMEC, INLE, ORO	Publication in Conference proceedings	VITAL-5G: Innovative Network Applications (NetApps) Support over 5G Connectivity for the Transport & Logistics Vertical	Konstantinos Trichias, Giada Landi, Erin Seder, Johann Marquez-Barja, Ronan Frizzell, Marius lordache, Panagiotis Demestichas	European Conference on Networks and Communications (2021 Joint EuCNC & 6G Summit,	2021 (accepted paper, pending presentation)
WINGS, NXW, IMEC, INLE, ORO, EBOS	Publication in IEEE Summit (invited paper)	VITAL-5G: Innovative Network Applications (NetApps) Support over 5G Connectivity for the Transport & Logistics Vertical	Konstantinos Trichias, Giada Landi, Erin Seder, Johann Marquez-Barja, Ronan Frizzell, Marius lordache, Vasileios Machamint	IEEE 5G for Connected & Automated Mobility (CAM) '21	2021
WINGS, EBOS NXW, IMEC, INLE, ORO,	5G-PPP related publication. (Not peer-reviewed)	VITAL-5G Project Description	Konstantinos Trichias, Vasileios Machamint, Giada Landi, Erin Seder, Johann Marquez-Barja, Ronan Frizzell , Marius lordache,	European 5G Annual Journal 2021 (6 th issue)	2021

Table 9: List of events attended by VITAL-5G Partners

Partner(s)	Type of activity	Place & Date of Activity	Title of the Activity	Description of the Activity	Size of Audience	Link
WINGS, EBOS, BEIA	Webinar	Online, March 5, 2021	5G-PPP Webinar - 5G Innovations for Verticals	Presentation of VITAL-5G Project by the Project Coordinator	120+	https://5g-ppp.eu/event/5g-ppp-webinar-5g-innovations-for-verticals/
DIAKINISIS	Industrial Event (Greek Language)	Online (Athens), March 10-11, 2021	Case Studies που δίνουν γνώση	VITAL-5G Project Presented in an industrial supply-chain oriented event	200+	https://www.supply-chain.gr/case-studies-%CF%80%CE%BF%CF%85-%CE%B4%CE%AF%CE%BD%CE%BF%CF%85%CE%BD-%CE%B3%CE%BD%CF%8E%CF%83%CE%B7-%CF%83%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%82-10-11-3-%CE%B1%CF%80%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%BF-supply-chain-institute/
WINGS, BEIA, EBOS	Virtual Summit	Online (Brussels) May 11-12, 2021	IEEE 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) Summit	Presentation of VITAL-5G Project by the Project Coordinator	100+	http://5gsummit.org/CAM/

5 Dissemination and Communication Activities Plan

The VITAL-5G Dissemination and Communication Activities' Time plan is subdivided into four major phases, based on the experience acquired by related projects, other works and best practices. Each of the dissemination and communication phases has its own objectives, target audiences, channels and goals, corresponding and parallel to the project progress. Figure 13 portrays the four phases, their spans, and the type of information associated with each phase. As can be seen in the figure, VITAL-5G is currently on the Awareness Creation Phase, where it mainly aims to create general awareness for the project to 5G and other stakeholders, leveraging on past experience of the project partners and their participation in the 5G-PPP programme.

Figure 13: VITAL-5G Dissemination & Communication Phases

The D&C phases are presented in detail in Table 10.

Table 10: VITAL-5G Dissemination and Communication Phases and Planning

Type of Information	Target Audience	Channels	Goals
Phase 1 (Awareness Creation) M0 – M12			
Presentation of VITAL-5G; Objectives of VITAL-5G; Expected results of VITAL-5G;	Industry, technological, research and academic communities; Potential end-users; International Stakeholders Group identified;	Conferences, workshops, congresses; Brochure and poster; Web site; Social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter);	General visibility; Attracting potential collaborators; Attracting potential customers Attracting potential investors.
Phase 2 (Impact Acceleration) M12 – M24			
Presenting elaborated use cases of VITAL-5G Demonstration and Prototype;	Potential end-users; Specific technological, research and academic communities;	Conferences, workshop; Publications in journals; Special session in congresses/conferences; Web site; Social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Exposing synergies with other 5G PPP projects; Providing visibility; Informing EC authorities; Attracting potential Collaborators.

Phase 3 (Results) M25 – M33			
Running results of VITAL-5G Demonstration and Prototype;	Potential end-users; Potential NetApp subscribers and app users; Specific technological, research and academic communities.	Conferences, workshops, congress; Publications in journals; Special sessions in conferences; Web site; Social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter).	Attracting potential investors; Attracting potential customers.
Phase 4 (Valorisation) M34 – M36 and >M36			
Final results of VITAL- 5G; User oriented demonstration;	Specific technological, research and academic communities; End-users and institutional organizations; Potential NetApp subscribers and app users.	Web site; Demonstrations; Publications in journal or press; Industry Focused events; Client demonstrations.	Attracting potential customers, investors; Informing the EC Authorities; Demonstrating results to existing customers.

6 Evaluation

This section presents the success indicators of the aforementioned dissemination and communication activities of the project through measurable targets that will be evaluated and measured throughout the lifetime of VITAL-5G, as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: VITAL-5G D&C Metrics, Success Indicators & Target Values

Communication/ Dissemination Means	Success Indicators	Target Values	Timeline
Project Website	Search Engine Optimization metrics	Online by month 1; Unique visitors from M12: 1000; from M36: 2000	Ready by M1; M1-M36
Social media	#of users/ followers	LinkedIn >200 followers; Twitter > 200 followers; Re-Tweets >200; Banners >30	M1-M36
Press Releases	# of press releases	Press releases >6;	M1-M36; 2 press releases per year
Newsletters	# of publications	Newsletters: >6	M1-M36; 2 Newsletters per year
Video Clips	# of video clips and views	Number of online video clips: >3; Number of video views: > 1000	By M36
Factsheets/ Brochures	# of factsheets and hardcopies	Technical factsheets: 3; Non-technical factsheets: 3; Hardcopies: > 1000	M1-M36

Flyers/ Posters & roll-ups	# of flyers and banners	Project flyers: >3; Posters & roll-up banners: >3	M1-M36
Industrial exhibitions	# of exhibitions	Participation in industrial exhibitions, trade fairs: >10	M7 -M36
Scientific publications	#of publications	Journals/magazines >10; Conferences >20; Conference demonstrations: >6	M7-M36
5G PPP programme	Active participation in 5G-PPP Working Groups (WGs)	Number of WGs to contribute: 7 Interactions with initiatives: > 4	M1-M36
Training	# of trainings over the course of the project	Online training tutorials: 3 Number of PhD schools: 2; Webinars: 2	M7-M36
Online Repository	Deliverables accepted by the European Commission	Number of publicly available deliverables: > 19	M1-M36

7 Conclusions

This report detailed the deliverable D6.2 'Dissemination and Communication Activities', which is one of the main outputs of Task 6.1: 'Dissemination & Communication Activities', performed within Work Package 6 'Dissemination, Communication & Standardization', which aims to maximize the impact of the project and disseminate the project results to key stakeholders of the T&L Sector.

This deliverable (D6.2) has included an overview of the design concept of the project's identity and has provided the initial dissemination and communication plan of the VITAL-5G project, along with its first implemented activities. Regarding the communication activities, the main target audience and activities have been identified, while the qualitative communication objectives have been presented in this report. The most important communication channels, such as the project's website, the factsheets, newsletters, and event organization have been listed. In regard to the dissemination activities, the target audience and the main dissemination channels of the project have also been identified. The most important dissemination channels, such as publications in scientific journals, participation in conferences and demonstration in exhibitions and EU events, have been listed. Furthermore, the time plan for all associated activities was reported. Finally, D6.2 has also provided the quantified targets and metrics for the dissemination and communication activities over a 3-year horizon.

This is a three-editions deliverable (M5, M18, M36). This first version mainly described the proposed D&C activities, tools, targets and phases, and aims to serve as a reference and support to the WP6 activities foreseen over the course of the project. The following deliverables (D6.3 and D6.4) will detail updates of the performed D&C activities on the first half and at the end of the project respectively.

Annex I: VITAL-5G First Press Release

PRESS RELEASE

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

VITAL-5G Project Commences

The H2020 ICT-41-2020 project VITAL-5G “Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities”, has commenced in January 2021 with a focus on showcasing the added value of 5G connectivity for the European Transport and Logistics (T&L) sector. This new EU-funded project held a successful online kick-off meeting on the 26th and 27th of January 2021, where the vision and the framework of the project were discussed. The multidisciplinary Project consortium consists of 16 partners from 6 countries and is coordinated by WINGS ICT Solutions.

VITAL-5G has the vision to advance the offered T&L services by showcasing the benefits of 5G-based Network Applications (NetApps) via real-life trials over state-of-the-art vertical (T&L) facilities (warehouse, hubs, ports) and advanced European 5G testbeds. To support both internal and 3rd-party experimentation, VITAL-5G will create an open, virtualized and flexible experimentation service portal and online repository which will facilitate the creation, deployment, monitoring and (re)configuration of NetApps in the vertical environment. Through its innovations, VITAL-5G will enable experimenters to experience ultra-fast service creation, dynamic customization of the service and flexible adjustment to real-time conditions.

The Project engages significant logistics stakeholders (Sea and River port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub logistic operators), Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), as well as innovative SME experimenters, thus prioritizing a multi-modal focus and addressing challenges of the entire 5G-enabled T&L ecosystem. Its results will be demonstrated in three 3GPP Rel.16 Stand Alone (SA) 5G testbeds: i) Telenet 5G Testbed in Antwerp (Belgium), ii) OTE 5G Testbed in Athens (Greece) and iii) Orange 5G Testbed in Galati (Romania).

"In VITAL-5G we aim to create 5G-enhanced services for the T&L industry by bridging the knowledge/expertise gap between the T&L sector, telecommunication experts and application developers, and as such we build on top of the knowledge, expertise and infrastructure of past research and innovation projects. Existing advanced 5G platforms (developed during previous H2020 projects) will be further developed during

the project, contributing to the faster adoption and enhanced penetration rate of 5G-based solutions in the T&L ecosystem." stated the VITAL-5G Project Coordinator, Mr. Konstantinos Trichias, from WINGS ICT Solutions.

Three use cases will be demonstrated to highlight the novelties of VITAL-5G: i) Automated vessel transport, ii) Data enabled assisted navigation & customs operations for ships and iii) Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics). The outcomes of these use cases will showcase the practical viability of VITAL-5G's solutions and the added-value of 5G connectivity for the European T&L sector. External experimenters will also be invited to test the VITAL-5G solutions and to even validate their own solutions and NetApps, using the VITAL-5G infrastructure and experimentation platform.

VITAL-5G, which is commissioned to run until December 2023, is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission with a budget of € 4.778 million. It brings together a strong consortium of major ICT, telecom and T&L stakeholders that will collaborate to achieve the goals of the project and ensure its successful execution.

Specifically the project consortium consists of:

WINGS ICT Solutions (Greece), **BEIA Consult International** (Romania), **DHL Exel Supply Chain Spain** (Spain), **Diakinisis S.A.** (Greece), **Digitrans** (Belgium), **EBOS Technologies Ltd** (Cyprus), **Asociatia Tehnopol Galati** (Romania),

Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum - IMEC (Belgium), **Incelligent IKE** (Greece), **Inlecom Group** (Belgium), **Compania De Navigatie Fluviala Romana Navrom** (Romania), **Nextworks S.r.l** (Italy), **Telenet Group** (Belgium), **Orange Romania** (Romania), **Hellenic Telecommunications Organization – OTE** (Greece) and **Seafar** (Belgium).

Further information for the project can be found at: <https://www.vital5g.eu/>

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